

Warm and Cold Detection Thresholds in Static and Dynamic Touch

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Abstract. Thermal perception in conditions of static touch (i.e. the detection of a transient temperature change when a stimulus is applied passively to the skin) has been studied extensively. In contrast, how mechanosensory signals arising from actively touching an object's surface may modulate thermal detection remains poorly characterised. This study investigated whether warm and cold detection thresholds differ between dynamic and static touch conditions in healthy participants. Thresholds were estimated using an adaptive Bayesian approach, allowing characterisation of both detection thresholds and slope of the underlying psychophysical function. Preliminary results showed no significant difference in warm detection thresholds or psychophysical slopes between conditions and provided mixed evidence that the cold detection threshold may be higher in dynamic touch. Further analyses, investigating the effects of skin temperature, hydration and normal force applied by the participants, are currently underway.

Keywords: Psychophysics, Thermoception, Two-Alternative Forced Choice.

1 Background

Ecologically, temperature estimation most commonly occurs during dynamic touch (DT), where thermal and mechanosensory inputs arise concurrently upon contact with a surface. The influence of simultaneous mechanosensory input on thermal detection however remains underexplored [1]. In addition, measured thermal detection thresholds are highly dependent on the psychophysical method employed, and existing approaches often involve a trade-off between accuracy and time required for the evaluation [2]. To our knowledge, no studies have systematically examined whether thermal detection thresholds are influenced by touch condition – specifically, whether participants actively touch the warm/cold surface producing concurrent mechanosensory input (DT) or whether their skin is passively exposed to a thermal stimulus (static touch, ST).

Open Research Questions and Interdisciplinary Exchange. This project aims to characterise how the touch condition may modulate thermal detection. The findings may be relevant for haptic devices incorporating thermotactile feedback, and we welcome discussions with haptics engineers on potential applications.

2 Methods

The study was approved by the UCLouvain Ethics Committee. Twenty-five healthy participants (17 females, 29.0±2.0 years, mean ±SEM) took part after providing writ-ten informed consent and received financial compensation for their participation.

A custom setup (Fig. 1a) combined a high-speed contact thermode (TCS-II QST.lab), allowing to control the temperature of the touched surface with 0.1°C precision and ramps of 75°C/s, mounted on a forces/torques sensor (mini40, ATI) to continuously monitor applied force. Skin hydration was measured using a Corneometer® (CM825, Courage + Khazaka electronic GmbH).

In the ST condition, participants maintained the index finger of their dominant hand in contact with the temperature-controlled surface set at baseline skin temperature. Each trial included two 5 s stimulation intervals spaced by 5 s and indicated by an LED shown to the participant (Fig. 1b). The thermal stimulus was presented in one of the two stimulation intervals, and participants performed a temporal two-alternative forced choice detection task. In the DT condition, the trial was identical except that the participant touched the surface with their finger only during stimulation intervals, and maintained it above the surface during the pause.

Warm and cold detection tasks were performed in two separate sessions on two separate days. Each session consisted of a block of ST trials and a block of DT trials (70 trials per block). The order of sessions and blocks was counterbalanced. Stimulation intensities were chosen using the adaptive Bayesian paradigm implemented via the Psi-method [3] (Palamedes Toolbox [4]). Finger temperature and hydration were measured at the beginning and end of each session, and during the pause between blocks (Fig. 1c). Room temperature was kept between 20-24°C.

3 Results

The psychophysical data were fitted using the Quick function,

$$\Psi(x;\alpha,\beta,\gamma,\lambda) = \gamma + (1-\gamma-\lambda) \times (1-2^{-(x/\alpha)^\beta}) \quad (1)$$

where α , β , γ and λ correspond to threshold, slope, guess rate and lapse rate, respectively. The function was refitted to the obtained data with a rectangular prior ($\alpha \in (0;10)$, $\log_{10}\beta \in (-1;3)$, $\gamma = 0.5$, $\lambda \in (0;0.1)$). Estimated thresholds relative to the skin temperature in DT and ST were not significantly different (Fig. 1d), both for warm (DT: 0.95±0.16°C, ST: 0.94±0.22°C, $p=0.96$, paired t-test) and cold (DT: -0.97±0.14°C, ST: -0.87±0.22°C, $p=0.36$) detection. Two participants showed outlier thresholds (>3°C) for both warm and cold detection in at least one of the two blocks. When removing these participants, there was no significant difference in warm detection thresholds (DT*: 0.77±0.09°C, ST*: 0.65±0.11°C, $p^*=0.34$). In contrast, the cold detection threshold was slightly but significantly increased in DT (DT*: 0.79±0.07°C, ST*: 0.57±0.09°C, $p^*=0.03$). There was no significant difference for the estimated slopes (Fig. 1e; normalised and log-transformed), both for warm (DT: 1.09±0.10, ST: 1.17±0.13, $p=0.63$) and cold (DT: 1.10±0.10, ST: 1.22±0.13, $p=0.32$) detection.

Fig. 1. Evaluation of thermal detection thresholds. a) Experimental setup. b) Static (ST) and dynamic (DT) touch trials. c) Experimental session structure. d) Warm and cold detection thresholds relative to the skin temperature (outliers indicated by a star; p-values reported before and after outlier exclusion). e) Warm and cold detection slopes.

4 Discussion

Our study represents a comprehensive approach to estimate psychophysical curves for thermal detection in dynamic and static touch. When using the entire dataset, there were no significant differences in thermal detection thresholds or psychophysical slopes. When excluding outliers based on abnormally high detection thresholds, only the cold detection threshold showed a significant increase in the DT condition. This suggests that the transient mechanosensory input that occurs upon touching a surface (DT condition) does not markedly modulate warm detection. Further analyses are needed to confirm the possible effect on cold detection. We are currently developing a hierarchical model to consider the contribution of additional factors, including skin hydration, skin temperature and participants' age. We will also analyse the force profiles to examine whether the applied normal force modulates thermal detection.

Acknowledgments. The study was funded by the ARC grant 24/29-141 from UCLouvain. BD is a Research Associate of the Fund for Scientific Research – FNRS, Belgium. The authors are thankful to the NTMD platform at IoNS for their technical support throughout the project.

Disclosure of Interests. No competing interests to declare relevant to the content of this article.

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